

FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL EDUCATION INDICATORS IN 1-4 TH GRADE STUDENTS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the content of the formation of indicators of spiritual education in students in grades 1-4, its current state.*

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Introduction. At a time when new reforms are being implemented and developed, it is necessary to emphasize the attention paid to education in the country. Upbringing and education are inseparable, these two processes are organized only on a mutually harmonious, continuous basis. It cultivates patriotic youth with a broad outlook and thinking, a modern profession. Theoretical and practical assistance to young people who are the builders of our future in acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities will pave the way for a more prosperous life tomorrow. We are stepping in line with new ideas and plans in the new Uzbekistan. These rapid steps will show their promising results in the near future.

The main part. It is also bearing fruit in the wide-ranging reforms in our society. In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 1059 of December 31, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation", the priorities of the Action Plan for the implementation of the Concept of continuous spiritual education marked. The purpose of the concept is to gradually form age-appropriate social skills and qualities necessary for an independent and happy life in the younger generation. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are required:

- Development of science-based indicators for the assessment of spiritual and moral education;
- effective use of the achievements of national and modern pedagogy in the upbringing of children;

- Regularly improve the knowledge and skills of educators as well as students;
- Spiritual education is based on the principles of gradual development and continuity.

According to him, the effective implementation of tasks, especially in the field of youth education, providing them with the basic competencies necessary for a peaceful life; development of science-based indicators for the assessment of spiritual education; Continuing the process of upbringing, based on the principles of continuity, first of all, the correct organization of the mother's pregnancy, spiritual upbringing of infants and children, parents, educators in the implementation of continuous spiritual upbringing from pregnancy to 30 years , a number of priorities, such as the development and implementation of a mechanism for mutually beneficial cooperation between teachers, continuing education institutions and the community. The concept states that our students should have the following spiritual and moral qualities from childhood (figure 1):

The Concept of Continuing Spiritual Education covers the following stages:

the first stage - in families (on the basis of two periods: the first period - the fetal period, the second period - the period from birth to 3 years);

second stage - preschool education from 3 to 6 (7) years;

the third stage - in the system of general secondary education (on the basis of two periods: the first period - 7 (6) - 10 years of primary school, the second period - 11 - 17 years of middle and high school);

the fourth stage - young people working and not engaged in production, as well as in the system of secondary special vocational and higher education institutions (on the basis of two periods: the first period -

secondary special vocational and young people not covered by higher education, as well as those engaged in production and not employed - 17 - 30 years, the second period - students of secondary special vocational, higher education institutions 15 - 22 (24) years old).

Our research topic covers the first phase of the third phase of the Concept - 7 (6) - 10 years of primary school. The formation of indicators of spiritual education in students in grades 1-4 today further increases the responsibility of the leadership of educational institutions, teachers. It assigns them the task of working tirelessly to increase the effectiveness of the tasks assigned to them. Students diligently study the knowledge, skills, and competencies imparted by the teacher. In order to teach, a teacher must first have thorough knowledge, high qualifications, skills and competencies with professional and life experience.

The teacher should take into account the following when educating students:

1. Taking into account the relevance of education to the mentality and age of students;
2. To study the impact of students' mental and spiritual relationships;
3. Literacy, art and skills of the teacher;

The determination of spiritual and moral qualities takes place on the basis of the following general content:

- The spiritual and moral level of students is reflected in the process of social relations, its approach to society, the environment and nature;
- The level of spiritual and moral development of students depends on the level of socio-spiritual development of society;
- The spiritual and moral development of students is the result of continuous, systematic education, organized on the basis of a combination of objective and subjective conditions;
- The spiritual and moral development of students leads to positive results in the establishment of social relations;

Spiritual education is the unification of spiritual consciousness, the development of moral feelings, and the formation of behavioral skills and habits. The purpose of spiritual and moral education depends on the requirements of society, which in turn depends on the level of development of the productive forces and the work of teaching and educating young people in society to form a moral and religious belief in the younger generation. should serve to educate them in the spirit of boundless devotion to the Motherland.

The primary school teacher performs the following tasks in the spiritual and moral education of students:

- a) Fostering students' commitment to society and the country;
- b) Fostering an ethical attitude to work;
- c) Ethical treatment of others;
- d) Fostering a moral attitude towards oneself and one's behavior;

Spiritual and moral education is a process of formation of spiritual and moral consciousness, giving students a structured knowledge of the essence of spiritual and moral relations, creating in them the need to acquire spiritual and moral knowledge. It must be organized in a consistent, continuous, systematic manner.

The organization of spiritual and moral education of students is a holistic process aimed at a specific goal, in which the following pedagogical tasks are solved:

1. Students are introduced to the essence of spiritual and moral norms and ethical relations and their importance in the life of society.
2. To create in students the need to acquire spiritual and moral knowledge, to determine the spiritual and moral consciousness.
3. To instill in students positive spiritual and moral qualities (knowledge, diligence, humility, humanity, love, devotion to the Fatherland, respect for parents and adults, generosity, devotion to duty, etc.).
4. Decide on the moral, ethical, character and will of students.
5. Formation of spiritual and moral culture of students.

The current state of formation of indicators of spiritual education in students of grades 1-4. At the heart of the reforms being carried out in our country today, the main goal is to bring up the younger generation in a fully developed and harmonious way. All the reforms in the field of education are aimed at improving the spiritual image of our children. It is necessary to recognize the implementation of the laws developed by our state in the development of young people as well-rounded individuals.

One of the most important tasks is to determine the formation of indicators of spiritual education in students in grades 1-4. We study the extent to which these aspects are formed in students of grades 1-4 in Termez city 16, 13 - general secondary school and Uzun district 5, 9 - general secondary school, which is the object of our research. We learned. From the observations made during our observations, we can say that in some students, real self-esteem, lack of high goals, mobilization for self-study, will, perseverance, diligence, we see that the qualities of action are not sufficiently developed, that their moral relations are not good, and that

these aspects also harm the quality of education. It also poses a number of challenges for our young people, who are entering independent life, to find their place in life, to make independent, positive decisions, and to become active individuals who benefit society.

With the implementation of large-scale reforms, the subject of "Education" has been included in the curriculum of secondary schools from the 2020-2021 academic year. The main essence of this science is to inculcate the qualities of spiritual education from an early age, to provide students with thorough knowledge, to strengthen the motivation for success, to teach diligence, career guidance, cooperation, the process of socialization with adults, national values. The study covers a number of tasks, such as the use of the rich scientific heritage of the ancestors, the development of spiritual and moral skills and abilities. It is the duty of today's parents, teachers and educators to inculcate spiritual and moral values in young people.

During our observations, we reviewed the "Education" textbooks for students in grades 1-4. Indicators of spiritual education are included in the textbooks. It explains the methods of pedagogical influence, gives examples by example. In the textbook for primary school, we found the following indicators of spiritual education (Table 1):

Indicators (criteria) of spiritual education			
1.	Loyalty to the motherland	20.	Respect for parents
2.	Greeting etiquette	21.	Remembering people
3.	Knowledge	22.	Perseverance
4.	Etiquette of talking on the phone	23.	Hard work
5.	Good manners	24.	Caution
6.	Common sense	25.	Dress culture
7.	The etiquette of sitting around the table	26.	Freedom
8.	Behavior in a public place	27.	Human etiquette
9.	Courage and bravery	28.	Graciousness
10.	Patriotism	29.	Respect for the elderly
11.	Reading	30.	Neighborhood etiquette
12.	Doing good	31.	Public transport etiquette
13.	Adamant	32.	Discipline
14.	Honesty	33.	Harmony
15.	Honesty	34.	Humanity

16.	Respect for the mother tongue	35.	Hospitality
17.	Savings	36.	Friendship
18.	Success	37.	The etiquette of giving and receiving gifts
19.	Obey the law	38.	Pilgrimage etiquette, etc.

Table 1. Indicators of spiritual education included in the textbook "Education" for primary school students (grades 1-4) of general secondary schools.

This table shows the indicators of spiritual education, which primary school students will master during the school year under the guidance of a teacher. In this case, the greatest responsibility falls on the teacher, who must always work on himself, to create new knowledge, to bring students to spiritual maturity, to bring them up as perfect human beings. At the heart of this work is the belief that the "beautiful character" - the "spiritually mature" people - will always be recognized. Along with educators, parents are also responsible for the expected results in this regard. The responsibility of educators is especially important in educational institutions. The research topic we are conducting leads to high rates of formation of spiritual education in primary school students. To further develop this process, we recommend a model for the formation of indicators of spiritual education. Through this model, students develop spiritual and moral competencies. In the future, they will be recognized as exemplary, well-rounded students with developed spiritual competence.

Conclusion. The formation of spiritual education in primary school students, in turn, requires teachers to develop their own spiritual maturity, the theory of spiritual and moral education, as well as spiritual and moral education in the school education process. requires a deep understanding of the enhancement methodology. In this regard, it is important to develop a coherent system of spiritual and moral education of students from the first stage of education. Enriching the content of teaching materials to form the spirituality of students in grades 1-4 on the basis of a holistic system, including art, historical works, fairy tales, stories and tales of Uzbek and world peoples, which will enrich the spiritual world of children. It is advisable to recommend winter, organize excursions to historical monuments, meetings with writers, poets, scientists.

The development program of Uzbekistan is aimed at raising the material and spiritual world of the people in setting long-term and long-

term goals, in-depth study, understanding and appreciation of the immortal heritage of the younger generation, in the spirit of universal values, modern science. parenting has become a priority. The values that ensure the existence of man and society are gradually passed down from ancestors to generations through spiritual upbringing. The term spiritual education in the broadest sense is a set of all spiritual influences, activities, actions, aspirations aimed at shaping the human personality, ensuring its active participation in production and social, cultural and educational life. Nurturing the spiritual qualities necessary for a person to live in a society is an ancient and eternal value that ensures its essence as a core value. There are also teaching materials that provide methodological support to teachers in the formation of indicators of spiritual education in the field of spiritual education, including methodological manuals in the field of spiritual education, more users of textbooks needed for students. The process of forming indicators of spiritual education will be further accelerated by referring to the public.

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